

SELL: THE ART, THE SCIENCE, THE WITCHCRAFT

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About Authors:

"Sell: The Art, the Science, the Witchcraft" is a book by Subroto Bagchi, offering insights into effective selling strategies. Published in 2017, it has gained acclaim as a valuable resource in the realm of sales and marketing.

Subroto Bagchi, co-founder of Mindtree Ltd, a pioneering Indian software services startup established in 1999, is renowned for his bestselling business books. Titles like *The High-Performance Entrepreneur* and *The Elephant Catchers* have been translated into numerous languages. Bagchi now serves as Chairman of the Odisha Skill Development Authority, where he focuses on promoting skill development, considering it his primary responsibility.

The book "Sell: The Art, the Science, the Witchcraft" by Subroto Bagchi is a captivating and comprehensive book that takes readers on a journey through the world of marketing management. In this humanized guide, Bagchi provides invaluable insights, practical advice, and relatable anecdotes to help readers navigate the complexities of marketing and apply effective strategies to their businesses or industries.

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SUMMARY OF 22 LAWS

The book opens with a profound insight into the core of Selling: "See me. Hear me. Invest in my message before my product. Let's negotiate terms. Spread the word. And return for more." This introduction establishes selling as a triad of Art, Science, and the Enchantment of Persuasion, each playing a crucial role in the process. Within this framework, each component plays a pivotal role in orchestrating successful transactions and fostering lasting connections with customers. By embracing this holistic approach, sellers can navigate the complexities of the marketplace with confidence and finesse.

The first leg, ART is identifying the target buyer and persuading them to buy the product when it is needed; The second leg, SCIENCE is the use of Technology and Psychology to understand the human behavior and use them for the betterment of selling process. The third leg, the MAGIC that lies with the seller(witchcraft) who converts seemingly impossible sales into successful sales through their persuasion traits.

The author emphasizes the significance of understanding the customer and to learn the Customer – Relationship Management (CRM). CRM is portrayed as a cornerstone of successful selling. The book talks about understanding the product from Top to Bottom and emphasizes that it is the key for the salesman to persuade customers into buying the product. The keen understanding of the product by the salesman makes it easier for him or her to explain to the customer conveniently which converts a lead into a customer. Believe the product completely so that you can confidently pitch that to your customers, much like McDonald's unshakeable confidence in the appeal of their hamburgers.

Also, it is important that the salesman needs to update his or her knowledge according to the current market situations. He explains them with his own personal experience, working as a Salesman for Computer Selling company in Delhi and various parts of the country. Not just having the trait of persuasion helps in converting a deal, it

is important to segment the product.

According to the need of the customer. Not every mail with potential customers you send, gets a respond. It is through the need of the customer that every product gets successfully sold. Even while in segmentation, it is important to be open all the time because people are uncertain and who becomes a prospect buyer at any time is also uncertain. As a salesman, we should not limit the sales.

Building relationships with the customer is crucial aspect of selling because it is not the product you sell, will attract the customers but how you sell will make the difference. The only constant is People buy from people. In today's digital world, online attractiveness becomes focal point with your webpage serving as the first impression. Salesman Job doesn't limit to just selling the product. They should portray themselves as consultants who provides solutions to the problems present. With effective solutions, they create lasting relationships which is the most important feature that makes any salesman to succeed. The book also underscores the significance of retaining customer over acquiring new customers.

In terms of how you sell the product, it is emphasized that there should a unique and value-driven approach to selling because people love weirdness and uniqueness. Add value to the customer rather than just being another compelling seller. There are many ways to sell a product, but a unique story behind the selling adds an essence for the product to get sold, as many customers will connect with the story which makes it easier for the salesman to convert the deal.

Another important aspect of selling is the negotiation skill. Both customer and seller have to benefit for mutually successful transaction, so that none lose their business. Be bold and courageous enough to ask for the negotiation which gives clarity on both sides.

There must be a continuous learning even in success and in the moments of failure. They should seek for constructive criticisms and feedbacks which advocate for day-by-day progress. They should be adaptable to every situation in this

rapidly changing world.

Aligning the thought process with the client and able to listen to them for the suggestion are presented as opportunities for the salesman to position him or her in the minds of the customer. (Joshi, K. R., & Anand, D. (2024))

It is important to pitch yourself above all. What is more important is being able to deliver the commitments you promised them in terms of product quality, services, delivery and so on. There should not be any legal consequences from the unfulfilled promises you have made as they can severely damage the reputation that you have earned in your lifetime. Customers look every corner of your business. So, it is important to facilitate the process as efficient as possible. The effective selling is not always grounded in logical decision but requires the understanding of the situations and be able to handle various situations without affecting the product sales. Being Authentic, Transparent and confident until the end of the deal is emphasized as the product is not sold till the paperwork is done.

Being grateful for the collaborative efforts that have been done for the years and embracing the success and failures which would take you beyond your potentials are essential for personal growth.

The book concludes with a list of attributes to become a champion seller;

1. **The Strategist:** One with a strategy to win.
2. **The Player:** The one who knows where to play and how to win.
3. **The Preparer:** Whose motto is to prepare, prepare, and prepare.
4. **The Winner:** Whose motto is to win, win, and win.
5. **The Purposeful:** The one who doesn't lose their purpose.
6. **The Storyteller:** The one who never loses their story delivery.
7. **The Olympian:** Like an Olympian, persevering.

8. **The Broad Viewer:** The one who takes the broad view.
9. **The Fearless:** The one who kills the fear.
10. **The Communicator:** The one who communicates effectively.

Learning objectives from the book

1. Gain an understanding of the Multifaceted nature of sales, encompassing both artistic and scientific elements
2. Exploring the different perspectives of psychological and emotional aspects of selling, including the role of influence, customer behaviour and persuasion.

Investigating the role of intuition and creativity in successful selling and to cultivate a mindset of continuous learning and development in sales field.

CONCLUSION

This book breaks it down for us in a way that's easy to understand. Whether you are a seasoned salesperson or just starting out, there's something for everyone here. Individuals who excel in sales not only meet our needs but also elevate the act of selling to a level where they serve and delight customers. Their approach leaves us happy and grateful, fostering relationships that we cherish and eagerly anticipate continuing. From understanding your customers to mastering the art of persuasion, this book covers it all. And even if you're not in sales, the insights shared can still help you navigate through everyday interactions and negotiations. In conclusion, selling is not just about pushing products; it's an art, a science, and sometimes feels like witchcraft! Remember, it's not just about making a sale; it's about building relationships and creating value for both parties. Happy selling!

REFERENCES

- Joshi, K. R., & Anand, D. (2024). Relevance of social exchange theory in B2B situation. *VLEARNY Journal of Business*, 1(1), 30–37.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1054123>